

d/d(ei/T) ln(p) as Probability Distributions in the Kaniadakis and Tsallis Cases

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In (1), we presented the relation: $\exp(-k\epsilon_i/T) \ln_k(p(\epsilon_i)) = \ln(p(\epsilon_i))$, where $\ln_k(p(\epsilon_i)) = -\epsilon_i/T$ for the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(\epsilon_i/T)$ in the $\epsilon_i/T \ll 1$ or $k \ll 1$ limit and argued that this was a way of seeing $\ln_k(p(\epsilon_i))$ linked to $\ln(p(\epsilon_i))$ through a Gaussian, i.e. a statistical distribution, at least in this limit. Thus, in the Kaniadakis case, $\ln(p(\epsilon_i))$ is not $-\epsilon_i/T$, but $-\epsilon_i/T$ multiplied by an unnormalized Gaussian weight. We showed that a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution applies for the Tsallis case instead of a Gaussian.

Here, we note that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case: $dp(\epsilon_i)/d(\epsilon_i/T) = -p(\epsilon_i)$ or $d \ln(p)/d(\epsilon_i/T) = -1$. If one considers 1 as a probability, then there is certainty for all ϵ_i . This leads to the idea that in a more general situation one might have $d \ln(p)/d(\epsilon_i/T) =$ a probability distribution. We pursue this idea by first considering some properties of the Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions.

In (2), it is shown that the Kaniadakis distribution $p(\epsilon_i) = \exp_k(\epsilon_i/T)$ satisfies: $dp(\epsilon_i)/d(\epsilon_i/T) = -1/\{\sqrt{1+k\epsilon_i/T}\} p(\epsilon_i)$. We argue that in the $\epsilon_i/T \ll 1$ limit or $k \ll 1$ limit this is approximately equivalent to:

$$dp/d(\epsilon_i/T) = -1/T p(\epsilon_i) \exp(-k\epsilon_i/T) \text{ or } d \ln(p)/d(\epsilon_i/T) = -1/T \exp(-k\epsilon_i/T) \quad (\epsilon_i/T \ll 1) \quad ((1))$$

The Gaussian, we argue, represents an unnormalized probability, so $d \ln(p)/d(\epsilon_i/T)$ shows how $\ln(p)$ changes from the physical information $-\epsilon_i/T$ and is in the form of a probability. We argue, as in (1), that this may be a signature of the Kaniadakis distribution, albeit one which only appears for $\epsilon_i/T \ll 1$ or $k \ll 1$. We show that in the Tsallis case, $d \ln(p)/d(\epsilon_i/T)$ is a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Thus, we suggest that if one did not know that the Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions existed, one could postulate that $d \ln(p)/d(\epsilon_i/T) =$ a probability distribution for a parameter k or $1-q$ being very small or $\epsilon_i/T \gg 1$. By trying a Gaussian and Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and insisting on a power law for $\epsilon_i/T \gg 1$, one could obtain these distributions.

$\exp(-k\epsilon_i/T) \ln_k(p(\epsilon_i)) = \ln(p(\epsilon_i))$

In (1), we obtained the relation: $\exp(-k\epsilon_i/T) \ln_k(p(\epsilon_i)) = \ln(p(\epsilon_i)) \quad ((2))$ for $\epsilon_i/T \ll 1$, through:

$$\ln_k(p) = 1/2k \{ p^k - p^{-k} \} \approx \ln(p) + \frac{1}{6} k^2 \ln(p) \ln(p) \ln(p) + \dots \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{For } k \ll 1 \text{ or } \epsilon_i/T \ll 1, \ln_k(p) \approx \ln(p) \exp(k^2 \ln(p) \ln(p) / 6) \quad ((4))$$

We now try to see the emergence of a Gaussian related to $\ln(p)$ in the Kaniadakis case in a different manner.

$$d \ln(p)/d(\epsilon_i/T) = -\exp(-k\epsilon_i/T)$$

In the Shannon case, $\ln(p(\epsilon_i)) = -\epsilon_i/T \quad ((5))$ so $d \ln(p(\epsilon_i))/d(\epsilon_i/T) = 1$. In other words, there is complete certainty (if one is taken as a probability) because ((5)) always holds. One might ask:

What if ((5)) does not always hold, i.e. yield the physical information. Is it possible to have $d\ln(p)/d(e_i/T)$ represent a particular probability distribution, in fact one which represents maximum randomness, i.e. a Gaussian in the $k \ll 1$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit/

In (2), the following differential equation is given:

$$dp/d(e_i/T) = - 1/ \{ \sqrt{1+kke_i/TT} \} p(e_i) \quad ((6))$$

In the $k \ll 1$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, ((6)) becomes:

$$d \ln(p(e_i))/ d(e_i/T) = - \exp(-kke_i/TT) \quad ((7))$$

In other words, $\ln(p(e_i))$ is no longer equal to $-e_i/T$ and so $d/d(e_i/T) \ln(p)$ does not equal 1. If one considers 1 to be a probability, then it represents complete certainty across all e_i . In the Kaniadakis case, this does not hold. One has an unnormalized Gaussian probability distribution representing the values of $d\ln(p)/d(e_i/T)$. This distribution holds in two limits:

$$k \ll 1 \quad \text{or} \quad e_i/T \ll 1 \quad (\text{or both}) \quad ((8))$$

((7)) is a result which follows from properties of the Kaniadakis distribution. The point we wish to make is that a Gaussian distribution is usually presented as representing maximum randomness. We suggest that one could develop the Kaniadakis formalism a priori by suggesting a Gaussian distribution for $d \ln(p)/d(e_i/T)$ as a statistical way of moving away from the Maxwell-Boltzmann case.

In such a scenario, one would postulate:

$$D \ln(p)/d(e_i/T) = c_1 \exp(- c_2 kke_i/TT) \quad \text{such that } k=0 \text{ or } e_i/T \rightarrow 0 \text{ yields the MB case} \quad ((9))$$

Here c_1 , and c_2 are unknown constants.

In the $k \ll 1$ limit or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, we argue that $p(e)$ should be equivalent to $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the first three orders (second order in $x=e_i/T$), i.e.

Let $p(x) = (1+kx + .5 k^2x^2 + \dots)$ power $1/k$ ((10)) (one needs at least second order because ((9)) is a Gaussian.

$$\text{Then } d\ln p/dx = (k+k^2x) / (1+kx+.5k^2x^2) = c_1(1-c_2k^2x^2) \quad \text{or}$$

$$\text{To second order in } x: \quad k(1-k^2x^2) = c_1(1-c_2k^2x^2) \quad \text{so } c_1=1 \text{ and } c_2=1. \quad ((11))$$

The next question is: What happens in the non $k \ll 1$ and non $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit? Examining ((10)), one may see that it is mathematically equivalent to:

$$(kx + \sqrt{1+k^2x^2}) \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((12))$$

The point of using ((12)) is that as $x \gg 1$, one has approximately: $(2kx)$ power $1/k$. If $0 < k < 1$, this yields a power law (see (2) which allows for $1/k$ and $-1/k$ as the power.

Tsallis Case

It seems that a similar differential equation should hold in the Tsallis case for which one has:

$$p(x) = \{1 + (1-q)x\}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} \quad \text{where } x = -e_i/T \quad ((13))$$

$$d \ln(p) / dx = 1/(1-q) p^{\text{power } (q-1)} = 1/(1-q) \exp(x(q-1)) \quad ((14))$$

Thus, $d \ln(p)/d(e_i/T)$ is a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution if $q-1 > 0$ with $x = -e_i/T$.

We suggest that one could consider $d \ln(p)/dx = c_1 \exp(xc_2)$ a priori and then try to obtain the Tsallis $p(x)$ ((13)) in a similar manner to that used in the Kaniadakis scenario. In particular, postulating an MB distribution means one only has to expand to first order in x i.e.

$$p(x) = (1 + (1-q)x)^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} \quad ((15)) \text{ to first order}$$

$$\text{Then } d \ln(p)/dx = 1/(1-q) \cdot 1/(1+(1-q)x) = c_1(1+xc_2) \quad \text{or } c_1=1 \quad c_2=q-1 \quad ((15))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that in the literature a differential equation is given for $dp/d(e_i/T) = -1/(\sqrt{1+kke_i/T}) p(e_i)$ for the Kaniadakis case (2). We suggest using this to obtain an expression for $d/d(e_i/T) \ln(p(e_i))$ and find that this is a Gaussian in the $k \ll 1$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limits. We suggest this means one has a random distribution associated with this derivative. In other words, $\ln(p(e_i))$ is no longer $-e_i/T$. We suggest that if one did not know the Kaniadakis distribution existed, one could have postulated a Gaussian form for $d \ln(p)/d(e_i/T)$ and then found the Kaniadakis result such that $e_i/T \gg 1$ yields a power law. We suggest a similar analysis for the Tsallis case, except that $d \ln(p)/d(e_i/T)$ is now a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and not a Gaussian. In other words, there seems to be a statistical basis, i.e. specific probability distributions, linked with $d \ln(p) / d(e_i/T)$ which yield the Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions such that they are power laws for $e_i/T > 1$. It is possible that there are other distributions which may be equated with $d \ln(p) / d(e_i/T)$ which might yield different statistical distributions other than the Kaniadakis and Tsallis ones.

References

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